

THE USAGE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract

As global interconnectedness increases, the value of acquiring a new language becomes more apparent. Whether for professional or personal reasons, the ability to communicate globally offers numerous advantages. Nowadays, the general aspiration of most higher education students is to employ efficient learning techniques for quick language acquisition and fluency. Therefore, English instructors in higher education are expected to be innovative, adaptable, and to identify the most appropriate methods tailored to each group or individual student. This article encompasses various contemporary approaches to teaching the English language.

Key words: interactive methods, teaching, process, effectiveness, modern education, brainstorming, learning.

The main task of modern education is not just to give the student fundamental knowledge, but to provide him with all the necessary conditions for further social adaptation and to develop a tendency towards self-education.

The modern educational system is characterized by:

- ✓ short training periods
- ✓ large amount of information received
- ✓ serious requirements for the level of knowledge, skills and abilities of the student or student

One of the main tasks for a current teacher is to make the learning process interesting for students, dynamic and modern. In addition, interactive technologies have come to the aid of teachers in this regard.

Interactive (“Inter” is mutual, “act” is to act) - means to interact, is in the mode of conversation, dialogue with someone. Interactive learning is a special form of organizing cognitive activity. Cognition is carried out in the form of joint activity of students. All participants in the cognitive process exchange information, interact with each other, solve problems, evaluate their own behavior and the actions of others, and simulate situations. In the process of communication,

conditions for comfortable learning are created, under which the student feels his success, his intellectual worth. [1]

The most common conversational methods include:

- ✓ Brainstorming (brain attack)
- ✓ Round tables (discussion, debate)
- ✓ Case study (analysis of specific situations, situational analysis)
- ✓ Business games, role-playing games
- ✓ Master classes

However, there are other widely used methods, such as Socratic dialogue, group discussions, training and interactive meetings. All these methods have in common their high efficiency and numerous advantages.

With active and interactive learning, students are largely subjects of educational activity and interact with the teacher and other students.

They become subjects of educational activities and interact with the teacher and other participants in the educational process.

Participates in the educational process and is actively involved in cognitive activities.

Actively participate in activities and perform creative, research and problem-solving tasks. Interaction between students

Interaction between students is achieved by completing tasks in pairs and groups. [2]

Each lesson in active learning (especially in a foreign language) is a kind of social environment in which the teacher and students enter into certain social relationships with each other, and the educational process represents the interaction of everyone present. In addition, successful learning is the result of the collective use of all learning opportunities. The use of role-playing games has wide possibilities for implementation of interactive learning. Role-playing is a methodology of active methods of teaching practical mastery of a foreign language. Role-playing creates conditions for real communication and thereby increases interest in the subject being studied. The use of role-playing games in teaching foreign languages at school is becoming increasingly widespread. As is known, educational role-playing games contribute to solving the most important methodological problems. This is the psychological preparation of children for language communication and ensuring the natural need to repeat language material repeatedly. [3]

Characteristics of interactive games in comparison with other active teaching methods among other active learning methods, interactive games perhaps have

more in common with role-playing games than with other active learning methods, but there are fundamental differences between them.

- ✓ In interactive games, there is no division into a group of role players and a group of observers,
- ✓ In interactive games, there is no division into a group of role-players and a group of observers participating in the analysis process.
- ✓ In interactive games, as in role-playing games, participants are given a situation. However, instead of specific roles, participants are given only instructions for action. In addition, the situation does not have to be similar to the real one.
- ✓ Interactive games are essentially reminiscent of sports competitions (the presence of a goal, participation, etc.), role-playing games close to the theater (roles, spectators, etc.). (Role-playing is similar to theater).

In conclusion, it should be noted that all interactive methods and techniques develop communication skills, contribute to the establishment of emotional contact between students, teach them to work in a team, listen to their peers, and establish closer contact between students and the teacher. Practice shows that the use of interactive methods and techniques in foreign language lessons relieves students' tension, gives them the opportunity to change the form of activity, attract the attention of the fundamentals new questions about the topic of the lesson. As a result, the quality of the presentation of the material and its effectiveness significantly increase acquisition, and therefore the motivation of students to learn a foreign language.

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